

ОРОЛ ДЕНГИЗИНИНГ ҚУРИГАН ТУБИДА ЎРМОН БАРПО ЭТИШ
САМАРАДОРЛИГИ

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Аннотация. Мақолада Орол денгизининг қуриган тубида Тахтақўпир давлат ўрмон хўжалиги томонидан ўрмонлаштириш ишларининг натижалари келтириб ўтилган. Ўрмон хўжалиги томонидан 8 минг гектарга яқин бўлган майдонда ўрмонлаштириш ишлари амалга оширилган бўлиб, экилган кўчатлар ва униб чиққан ниҳолларнинг яшовчанлиги 40% дан юқори бўлганлиги қайд этиб ўтилган

Калит сўзлар: Орол денгизи, шамол оқими, кўчат экиш, уруғ сепиш, қум тўпловчи жўяклар, яшовчанлик.

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ЛЕСОВОССТАНОВЛЕНИЯ В ПРИАРАЛЬЕ

Аннотация. В статье приводятся результаты лесоразведочных работ Тахтакупирским государственным лесхозом на высохшем дне Аральского моря. Лесным хозяйством проведена лесовосстановительная работа на площади около 8 тыс. га. отмечено, что всхожесть посаженных саженцев и проросших всходов превышает 40%.

Ключевые слова: Аралский море, поток сила, посадка саженцев, посев семян, бороза сбора песков, проживаемость.

EFFICIENCY OF REFORESTATION IN THE ARAL SEA

Annotation. The article presents the results of forest exploration by the Takhtakupir State Forestry on the dried-up bottom of the Aral Sea. Forestry carried out reforestation work on an area of about 8 thousand hectares. it was noted that the germination of planted seedlings and germinated seedlings exceeds 40%.

Key words: Aral Sea, the flow of power, planting seedlings, sowing seeds, furrow collecting sand, livability

Introduction. As a result of droughts observed in recent years, various climate changes are taking place in many areas. As a result, dramatic changes were also observed in a number of water bodies. One such basin is the Aral Sea. According to scientists, the Aral Sea, once recognized as one of the largest lakes on earth, has now become one of the areas in need of attention.

Up to 72 million tons of sand and dust are released into the atmosphere every year from the dried bottom of the Aral Sea, which creates an ecological crisis in the Aral Sea region. Due to the drying up of the Aral Sea, the salinization process in the Aral Sea region has sharply increased, which has led to the formation of salt and dust in the air, intensified environmental tensions, and increased the spread of serious diseases among the local population. The productivity of agricultural crops declined, and the process of desertification began to develop.

One of the factors that reduces the process of deflation on the dried bottom of the Aral Sea and reduces the amount of dust, salt in the air, purifies the air, increases the amount of carbon

dioxide in it by increasing oxygen is the rapid development of forest reclamation, which improves the ecological situation in the Aral Sea region. The establishment of forests solves three main problems:

- Reduces the kinetic energy of the wind, strengthens the soil particles with the roots, which reduces the process of deflation, ie prevents the rise of salt, dust and sand;
- from the dried bottom of the sea will allow the development of animal husbandry, beekeeping and the growth of medicinal plants;
- Forests consisting of trees and shrubs improve the ecological situation, they absorb carbon dioxide. Increases oxygen, collects dust.

Scientific research shows that a 4-year-old saxophone planted on one hectare of land releases 1,158 m³ of oxygen. It is also important to ensure the purity of nature at a time when atmospheric air is becoming increasingly polluted. One saxophone can hold 4-4.5 tons of sand dunes a year [5, 9].

Numerous studies have been conducted on the use of forest trees and shrubs in the consolidation of mobile sands, which have resulted in the widespread use of plants such as saxaul, cherkez, kandym, yulgun, depending on the soil conditions of the area [1, 8, 10]

The first production and experimental work on the enrichment of desert pastures on the basis of agroforestry methods began in 1925-1927. Preliminary research was conducted at the Bogdin Research Station. These studies date back to 1946 when I.A. Keyzer [6].

The first work on pasture reclamation in Uzbekistan was carried out in 1948-1949 by G.A. Carried out by Sergeeva, in the saline-ephemeral pastures of the Karnob desert, black saxaul meadow-protected forest rows were established. In 1961-1964, Shafirkan Forestry established 8,725 hectares of black saxaul reserves. Research has been carried out extensively since 1969 by the Karakul Research Institute [7]. Pasture enclosures have been established through the widespread use of these measures in mountain pastures with an annual rainfall of 150-200 mm [2-4].

Object and method of research. The research was carried out in saxophone reserves built on the dried bottom of the Aral Sea. The saxophone reserve is considered to have started in 2018 on the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev. According to the State Committee for Forestry, by 2020, a number of measures have been taken on the dried bottom of the Aral Sea (Table 1).

Table 1

WORK DONE ON THE DRY BOTTOM OF THE ARAL SEA

№	Events	Year	
		2018 – 2019	2019 – 2020
1	Reforestation	501	703
2	Sowing the seeds	400	663
3	Planting seedlings	61	40
4	Pasture construction	0	3.0
5	Getting sand-collecting ditches	1250	130
6	Prepared seeds, thousand tons	1,5	2,8

The degree of natural recovery of saxophones was studied on the basis of VG Nesterov's method, and experimental plots of 1x1 and 2x2 m² were allocated for analysis. The amount of 1- and 2-year-old saxophone seedlings in them was statistically analyzed using special formulas to determine the degree of natural recovery of saxophones in the area.

Research results and their discussion. The assessment of the condition of the saxophones was carried out in the areas where sowing and planting were carried out.

When the growth of plants planted in different phytocenoses was observed, many planted ameliorants began to germinate in the first decade of April and fully germinated by the middle of the second decade of April. In the spring, an average of 2,000-3,250 black saxophones sprouted at a distance of 100 m from the enclosures. But in the short term, the survival of existing saxophone seedlings has declined sharply. This is due to a decrease in soil moisture, varying degrees of salinity of the surface layer.

As a result of salinization of the soil surface layer, the originally planted plants in many areas have dried up. Plants planted in enclosures built on saline-brown soils quickly stopped growing under the influence of salinity. Plants planted in strongly saline soils were damaged and dried up in the first and second years.

The results of the study of the viability of seedlings and seedlings planted as a result of seeding in saxophones were as follows (Table 2).

Table 2

Results of construction of saxophones in the territory of Takhtakopir state forestry

№	Years of work completed	The method of building a saxophone	Built area, e	Survival of saxophones, %
1	2018	From seed	1343	44,5
		From seedlings	909	45,7
2	2019	From seed	1443	40,2
		From seedlings	817	48,4
3	2020	From seed	2502	35,8
		From seedlings	759	44,2

As can be seen from the table above, 5,288 hectares of saxaul were planted in the Takhtakor State Forestry Area between 2018-2020 by sowing seeds and 2,485 hectares by planting seedlings. Their survival rate was 35.8-48.4%.

Conclusion. Deforestation of the dried bottom of the Aral Sea is one of the most important measures, and the work carried out by the Takhtakor State Forestry covers a total of 7773 hectares. The effectiveness of the work done in these areas can be seen in the fact that the viability of young saxophones is 35.8-48.4%.

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